

BARS OF HOPE: THE CONCEPT OF “PAG-ASA” FOR TATAYS WHO SERVE LONG-TERM IMPRISONMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the concept of “*Pag-asa*” for *Tatays* who serve long-term imprisonment in the Philippines and its influence on their fatherhood experiences, resilience and personal belief systems. This study also deemed to answer how “*Pag-asa*” influenced their belief systems, their daily lives, and paternal roles as fathers. Using qualitative approach and semi-structured interviews with six (6) long-term imprisoned fathers, the study revealed that “*Pag-asa*” is deeply rooted in familial bonds, faith in God and in Philippine prison community practices, providing spiritual resilience as well as emotional strength for the imprisoned *Tatays*. The findings also revealed that “*Pag-asa*” helped these fathers to maintain their positivity, purpose, and endurance despite being imprisoned. Furthermore, the study affirmed that “*Pag-asa*” is an integral supplement for the resilience and fatherhood of these imprisoned *Tatays*. This study emphasizes the need for tailored interventions that strengthen familial, spiritual, and community connections to enhance resilience and foster “*Pag-asa*” among imprisoned fathers.

Keywords: “*Pag-asa*”, Fatherhood, Filipino *Tatay*, resilience, Imprisonment

INTRODUCTION

Fathers have an important role and make a significant contribution to children’s emotional, social, financial, as well as to the overall welfare of their children. Instilling values and guidance to them; striking balance between these aspects, a daunting task

which determines the welfare of these children, involves these duties of fatherhood which requires a thoughtful and demanding approach to ensure these children's needs are met (Carlson, 2020).

In the pursuit of justice, imprisonment serves therefore for criminal acts and statistics show a vast disparity in demographics, with men constituting a higher proportion of the prison population compared to women. In 2021, male imprisonment rate was over 6 times higher than that of females (Bureau of Justice Statistics, 2021). Further compounding, a substantial portion of these imprisoned men are fathers. A study reveals that the number estimation suggests that over half of them have children (Glaze & Marushack, 2019). These fathers who are confined within these prison walls, separated from their families, face a difficult path to maintain their relationship with their children which casts shadows on their future.

Regardless of grim reality and disarray associated with imprisonment, recent research underscores that people have the capacity of feeling hope, even under the circumstances of being imprisoned (National Fatherhood Initiative 2023; The Marshall Project, 2023).

"*Pag-asa*" is from the related words "*pag*" which is a conjunction meaning "on" and "*asa*" which is a verb meaning "to hope." As defined in the Filipino Dictionary. Going beyond the traditional idea of hope, the Filipino idea of "*Pag-asa*" is the assured expectation of promised blessings of God, which helps people find joy in life, and gives resilience amidst adversity (The CJCLS- Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, 2024).

In addition, "*Pag-asa*" represents atonement for Filipinos, regardless of whether our sorrow is caused by external factors or not. Thus, there is hope as the idea of redemptive suffering is highlighted. "*Pag-asa*" is a crucial measure of wellbeing, especially for those who are distressed or live in difficult situations (Louis, 2020).

This research's main objective is to investigate the meaning of "*Pag-asa*" among Filipino *Tatay's* under long term imprisonment. This notwithstanding, the Philippine legislations do not give a clear definition of either long-term imprisonment or specific time frame under which such a term is applicable even though a lot has been done in this regard by researchers. In this context, it may be referred to as a sentence of not less than ten years plus life imprisonment according to international standards (Webster, 2024).

This study intends to resolve an important gap in research, that is, the experiences of Filipino *Tatay's* who have been jailed from ten (10) to twenty (20) years and the extent to which "*Pag-asa*" has been important in their lives. This research also supports the formulation of family-and community-based development programs and is closely related to the importance of identifying the sources of "*Pag-asa*" to these fathers, how these have been helpful to them in their long-term imprisonment, and what possible interventions could enhance this critical asset. Therefore, the researchers utilized qualitative methodology and intensive interviewing techniques to tap into various aspects of "*Pag-asa*" in the prison environment.

Research Questions

Central Question

How does the concept of *Pag-asa* impact the fatherhood experiences of those who serve in long-term imprisonment in the Philippines?

Corollary Questions

1. What is "*Pag-asa*" for *Tatay*'s who serve long-term imprisonment?
2. In what way does "*Pag-asa*" affect their everyday lives?
3. How does "*Pag-asa*" affect their belief system as a *tatay*?
4. How does their belief in "*Pag-asa*" influence their role in fulfilling their duties to their children?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A study employed a qualitative research design strengthened with phenomenology for investigation into "*Pag-asa*" among Filipino *Tatay* serving minimum sentences of 10 to 20 years in the Muntinlupa Bilibid Prison. Through this design, the researchers found the basic subjective constructions and encounters made by participants on the concept of "*Pag-asa*" among *Tatay* who served long-term imprisonment.

In line with their desired results, the researchers employed IPA (Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis), which consisted of analysis of subjective data with identifying patterns (Fieldsend & Smith, 2021) in developing a theory of the concept of "*Pag-asa*" among imprisoned *Tatay*. IPA enabled participants to present their thoughts and stories considerably without bias by emphasizing, rather, their mutual experience.

Research Locale

The research was conducted at Muntinlupa Bilibid Prison or New Bilibid Prison. This is a prison run by the Bureau of Corrections (BuCor) and is one of the biggest prisons in the country, supposed to have very tight supervision for high-profile prisoners or those convicted criminals in need of strict surveillance. According to Bolledo (2022), as of the date of October 2022, the New Bilibid Prison had a total number of inmates of 29,204, approximately 4.6 times higher than the ideal capacity of 6345. This was found relevant and appropriate by the researchers-the NBP in that it offered a broad range of subjects as potential participants for this study.

Population and Sampling

In this qualitative research, researchers made use of purposive sampling, the sampling is proper that allows the researcher to pick participants base on the criteria for

choosing an individual that possesses relevant characteristics and experiences for investigating the phenomenon and to the research question.

Using the appropriate purposive sampling that helps to gather valuable data of incarcerated fathers who can contribute in an explicit manner with regards to their experiences, which means this approach will facilitate bringing together the collected data straight with the research goals it will provide a detailed rich comprehension about the concept and the phenomenon with reference to being imprisoned (Wu & Guballa, 2023)

Participants of the Study

Through purposive sampling, the researchers selected six (6) participants fitting into the eligibility criteria outlines that have been set for this study: all these participants are *Tatay* serving long-term incarceration ranging from ten (10) to twenty (20) years in Muntinlupa Bilibid Prison. They should not be convicted of child abuse or any other related violations. This ensures that participants exhibit pure intentions and love toward their children, thereby making their responses reliable and valid. Under these conditions, data collection can be directly aligned with study goals to amass rich understandings of the construct and phenomenon within incarceration context.

Instrument of the Study

Researchers utilized interviews as a research instrument and will ask open-ended questions to give the participants a chance to express their thoughts clearly. This study will use semi-structured questions created by the researchers that will help gather in-depth information based on participants' answers to attain the desired result. It also helps the research have direction and be fully tracked (Mashuri, S. et al., 2022).

Guide questions and one-on-one interviews will be distributed to six (6) participants. Researchers will use eight (8) guide questions followed by sub-questions based on their answers.

1. **What does “Pag-asa” mean to you? Can you describe it?** (*Ano ang ibig sabihin ng “Pag-asa” para sa iyo. Paano mo ito ipapaliwanag?*)
2. **As a Filipino Tatay, what is “Pag-asa” to you and where do you find it?** (*Bilang isang Pilipinong ama, ano sa tingin mo sa “Pag-asa” at saan mo ito maaring kunin o hanapin.*)
3. **Are there any instances that “Pag-asa” influences you in coping with long-term imprisonment? What are those?** (*Mayroon bang mga pagkakataon na ang “Pag-asa” ay nakatulong sa iyo sa pagharap sa pangmatagalang pagkakakulong? Ano-ano ang mga iyon?*)
4. **As a Filipino Tatay, how does your cultural understanding of “Pag-asa” shape your experience of hope or its absence while serving long-term imprisonment? How do you say so?** (*Bilang isang Pilipinong ama, paano hinubog ng iyong pangkulturang pagkaunawa sa “Pag-asa” ang iyong karanasan ng pag-asa o kakulangan nito habang nagsisilbi ng pangmatagalang pagkakakulong? Paano mo nasabi?*)

5. **How does “Pag-asa” influence your fatherly role of duties?** (*Paano nakakaimpluwensya ang "Pag-asa" sa iyong tungkilin bilang ama.*)
6. **In what ways has your “Pag-asa” been challenged or strengthened?** (*Sa anong mga paraan hinamon o pinatatag ang iyong “Pag-asa”?*)
7. **What is the external support system contributed to your sense of “Pag-asa”? Can you provide examples of resilience and how trust in positive outcomes contributed to your “Pag-asa” during these times?** (*Ano ang naging kontribusyon ng iyong panlabas na suporta (mga bagay o tao na hindi parte ng iyong sarili ngunit ay sumusuporta sa'yo) sa iyong pagkakaroon ng pakiramdam ng "Pag-asa"? Maaari ka bang magbigay ng mga halimbawa ng pagiging matibay at kung paano nakatulong ang tiwala sa positibong mga kinalabasan sa iyong pakiramdam ng "Pag-asa" sa mga panahong ito?)*)
8. **What can you recommend to other fathers who are also in long-term imprisonment about maintaining or finding “Pag-asa”?** (*Ano ang maaari mong irekomenda sa ibang mga ama na nasa pangmatagalang pagkakakulong tungkol sa pagpapanatili o paghahanap ng “Pag-asa”?*)

Validation of the Instrument

The research instrument was validated by consonance with the opinion of advisory research followed by three experts- psychometrician, psychologist and professors associated with law or any job correlated to the study-for establishing content and construct validity. Incorporation of all corrections and suggestions of the above-mentioned experts and validators made this instrument disseminated.

Data Gathering Procedures

To the data-gathering procedure, researchers first had to acquire the required documents-including letters, permits, and consent forms-from the not only participants but also other people monitoring the participants being included in the study. All required documents needed to gain approval for conducting the data-gathering procedure were submitted to the concerned office(s) in Muntinlupa Bilibid Prison. Only when the researchers received the official clearance of their application did they initiate the data-gathering procedure. The gathering of data would take at least a day for every person involved, although this may lengthen its period due to any impediment that might be seen along the way. Modality, date, and execution, for that matter, will follow the protocol which Muntinlupa Bilibid Prison has followed. The responses of the participants were recorded both in audio and written forms. After the data-gathering process, all the data collected was then transcribed and analyzed to provide the researchers with the information they needed.

Treatment of the Study

The researchers adopted Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) for the exploration of experiences amongst the participants. IPA differed the experiences of phenomena from others and made them distinctive. It was also dynamic in nature and played a role of an active person that made the participants accommodate the

researchers into their life experience. Further to this, it is stated that IPA is a process of double interpretation and double hermeneutic because the interpretations regarding their world by participants and subsequent sorting out of the information by researchers are involved to understand their experiences.

In the process of looking for themes or recurring patterns, it was highly pivotal to carry out a proper analysis by reading and re-reading the transcript to ensure proper familiarity with what was inside the transcript. Furthermore, reading the transcript multiple times provided the researchers with a new perspective, as each reading session had the potential to instill a different way of interpretation and, therefore, a different insight. A transcript from a single participant could have been analyzed or written up as a case study on its own. However, a more common practice was to analyze such materials while incorporating multiple transcripts from multiple participants. The themes emerged in each transcript could also have been used as a guide for the interpretation of any of the following transcripts. The investigators could have chosen to do all the data simultaneously gathered. Whatever the method selected, the researcher had to be independent in terms of the facilitation to accept and interpret emergent patterns while also not ignoring any problems that may have arisen as they followed up on the transcripts (Pietkiewicz & Smith, 2014).

Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensured all ethical considerations by providing the participants with a consent form to sign. This ensured that all the participants were cooperating willingly and were not coerced to take part in the study. Moreover, the form indicated that the researchers are committed to maintaining their responsibility of not revealing any information that would be provided by the participants.

Research, interviews, consultation services, or similar ventures without the participants' informed consent are punishable under the law. The law clearly stated that all individuals functioning as respondents or participants must first be oriented and asked to approve the provision of information and for such information to be used and processed. Similarly, they should be assured that all documents, information, and recordings they provide or are a part of would be kept safely. Conclusion In a nutshell, the researchers, interviewers, or any person asking for information from others had the responsibility to explain the necessity of participants' disclosure of information. They were also mandated to advise participants on the risks of privacy, especially during electronically conducted and recorded data-gathering procedures (PAP, 2022).

This also implied that the Data Protection Act was enacted to ensure people's privacy concerning their human rights. It would guarantee private information and communication systems from invasion by the private sector or government.

RESULTS

1. What is “Pag-asa” for *Tatay*’s who serve long-term imprisonment?

Thematic Chart A

CENTRAL THEMES	SUB-THEMES	DESCRIPTION	CODES
1. The family as a main source of “Pag-asa”	1.1 Family as Strength	<p>P1: Participants “Pag-asa” to go back home and offer care and guidance to their grandchildren.</p> <p>P4: Participant finds “Pag-asa” in children, implying that their volumes and attachment towards children are the main sources of their cause in life and strength to endure.</p>	Anak, pamilya
	1.2 Emotional Resilience for Family	<p>P1: Participants gets strength and motivation from their children, the well-being of which makes them feel strong enough to withstand whatever happens.</p> <p>P2: Participant empowers happiness even in the sad times as they would hold on to making happy.</p>	Malungkot pero masaya

<p>2. “Pag-asa” through Faith</p>	<p>2.1 Faith in God as “Pag-asa”, resilience and support</p>	<p>P3: Participant places faith in God and is hopeful that this will carry and guide them through their struggles.</p> <p>P5: Participant emphasizes reliance on God as the source of “Pag-asa” and strength, solidifying their spiritual connection through times of distress.</p> <p>P6: Participant says that prayer is of utmost importance it is indeed a significant source of strength that can carry the believer through trials and doubts.</p>	<p>Panginoon, tiwala, dasal</p>
<p>3.External Support System: Pillar of “Pag-asa” in Long-term imprisonment</p>	<p>3.1 Family Support</p>	<p>P1: Participant shows how communication from family outside is a profound source of happiness and “Pag-asa”.</p> <p>P6: Participant clearly states how strength and “Pag-asa” from family’s encouragement contributes to</p>	<p>Komunikasyon</p>

		resilience and strength despite the incarceration.	
	3.2 Act of Kindness from the Religious Support Groups and Community	<p>P3: Participant shares how gestures of kindness from religious groups such as giving gifts, contributes to unwavering happiness and feeling that they are loved and never forgotten especially that they are incarcerated for a long period of time.</p> <p>P5: Participant shows appreciation from the support received from religious groups clearly envisions this as act of care which serves as their beacon for their encouragement and continued “Pag-asa” despite the incarceration.</p>	Bigay na suporta

2. In what way does “Pag-asa” affect their everyday lives?

Thematic Chart B

CENTRAL THEMES	SUB-THEMES	DESCRIPTION	CODES
1. Pag-asa: A Catalyst for Emotional Endurance and Strength of Filipino Incarcerated Tatays	1.1 Pag-asa as source of strength for the future	<p>P1: Participants visualize the future and readiness to contribute and work hard after incarceration.</p> <p>P4: Participant reflects in a better future, motivating to remain strong and prepare in life after imprisonment</p>	“Pag-asa” influences the participants to visualize a better future which inspires them to work.
	1.2 “Pag-asa” as Strength to Endure	<p>P6: Participant endures emotional and mental challenges during incarceration showing the function of hoe as an integral source of resiliency. (participants’ visibly shows strength the way he tells story of overcoming conflict and challenges within the prison environment.)</p> <p>P1: Participant significantly shows mental strength and</p>	Participant’s “Pag-asa” reinforces their ability to face day-to-day challenges in their mental being as well as physical being.

		endurance that reinforces the ability to cope with courage and to endure loneliness and physical challenges inside the prison environment.	
2. Strengthening and Challenging “Pag-asa”	2.1 Faith and Religion as a source of continued “Pag-asa” amid adversities	<p>P1: Participants emphasized that their belief in God is central to maintaining “Pag-asa”, especially when facing personal struggles and challenges.</p> <p>P4: The participant always has faith in the Lord.</p> <p>P6: Through faith in God, the participant finds strength.</p>	Faith-driven resilience
	2.2 Pessimism and loss of faith	<p>P5: Participants emphasized how the reality of their situation imposed a negative outlook in life which resulted in their loss of “Pag-asa” and challenged faith</p> <p>P6: The participant has no faith in God.</p> <p>P4: The</p>	Overcoming physical and emotional struggles

		participant was deeply saddened by what happened to him.	
	2.3 “Pag-asa” Through Family and Communication	<p>P5: Despite challenges, participants find “Pag-asa” and strength through communication with their family, including calls and messages, even from prison.</p> <p>P2: The participant only communicates with his one child who works at the provincial jail.</p>	Emotional connection and support from family

3. How does “Pag-asa” affect their belief system as a *tatay*?

Thematic Chart C

CENTRAL THEMES	SUB-THEMES	DESCRIPTION	CODES
1. Familial bonds as a precursor of “Pag-asa” towards influencing a positive belief system on their incarcerated life.	1.1 Familial bonds inspire “Pag-asa”, which drives them to respond to their situation positively.	<p>P1: Participant draws “Pag-asa” from their physical health and from his children and grandchildren.</p> <p>P2: Participants draw “Pag-asa” from seeing their family once again.</p> <p>P5: Participants draw “Pag-asa” from their family.</p> <p>P6: Participants draw strength from their family.</p>	<p>Pamilya ang “Pag-asa” at Lakas</p>
	1.2 Desire for Freedom and Reconnection	<p>P2: Participant indicates a yearning to come and reunite with the family.</p> <p>P3: Participant statement signifies patience and a great yearning for some opportunity to start life again outside the confinement.</p>	<p>“Pag-asa” for release and family reunion</p>
	1.3 “Pag-asa” as a source of resilience Despite	<p>P2: Participant words speak of a deep dependence</p>	<p>“Pag-asa” amidst</p>

	Challenges	<p>on faith and an ardent longing for freedom with divine help.</p> <p>P4: Participant says that life bears optimism.</p>	adversity.
2. "Pag-asa" as a foundation of positivity	2.1 "Pag-asa" as a Spiritual Anchor	<p>P1: Participants have "Pag-asa" as long as they lean on God.</p> <p>P5: Participant words come from such resilience and a solid reliance on something inside. That whatever happens, their faith would stand firm.</p> <p>P6: Participant says that the promise of "Pag-asa" is based on faith and states that "Pag-asa" would be something that one could really rely on all because it comes from God. It is assurance and confidence in divine guidance.</p>	"Pag-asa" as a foundation of peace
	2.2 "Pag-asa" as Endurance	P6: Participants exhibit a very resilient attitude,	Enduring life's struggles through "Pag-

		<p>believing that no matter the challenges they may face, they won't be unable to deal with them.</p> <p>P5: Participant speaks profoundly about an enduring “Pag-asa”, firmly rooted in faith despite life's uncertainties or possible imprisonment.</p>	asa”,
3. Faith, Community, and Resilience as Cultural Roots of “Pag-asa” in Filipino Imprisonment.	3.1 Religious Practices of Filipino Incarcerated Fathers as Reinforcement of “Pag-asa”	P2, P3, P4, and P5: Participant's describe how religious gatherings and participation nurture faith, community bond and boost “Pag-asa”.	Participant emphasized how their spiritual participation within the prison environment helps them as Filipino tatay to become hopeful despite an extended period of time.
	3.2 “Pag-asa” through community and purposeful Actions and self-reliance	<p>P6: Participant believes that doing good deeds brings purpose and “Pag-asa”.</p> <p>P1: Participant indicates how self-reliance combined with purposeful work sustains “Pag-asa” even within the constraints of</p>	Participants shows how Filipino cultural values shape “Pag-asa” as an interplay between communal and purposeful actions

		incarceration.	
4. Spiritual Faith sustaining "Pag-asa" in Long Term Imprisonment	4.1 Power of Prayer	<p>P1: Participant have the conviction that God is the number one supporter that evokes participant's optimism and resilience.</p> <p>P4: Participant state faith as the central source of "Pag-asa".</p> <p>P5: Participant believes that faith is a stable force that prevents loss of "Pag-asa".</p>	Prayer as a source of strength
	4.2 Encouraging and Guiding Others	<p>P5: Participant encourages everyone to see life as a beacon of opportunity and to also maintain "Pag-asa".</p> <p>P1: Participant wants to achieve goals to serve as inspiration for peers and loved ones.</p>	Supporting others through faith and particularly through prayer, personal spiritual practices that encourage others how faith is a shared foundation for positivity and resilience.

4. How does their belief in “Pag-asa” influence their role in fulfilling their duties to their children?

Thematic Chart D

CENTRAL THEMES	SUB-THEMES	DESCRIPTION	CODES
<p>1. “Pag-asa”, Faith, and Family Responsibility</p>	<p>1.1 Family as a support mechanism and a source of “Pag-asa”</p>	<p>P1: Participants expressed that their family, especially children, is a source of strength and motivation helping them maintain “Pag-asa” while imprisoned.</p> <p>P4: The participant hoped for their family to be whole again.</p> <p>P5: The participant seeks to see his family when he is still alive.</p>	<p>“Pag-asa” from children and family</p>
	<p>1.2 Faith and Religion as a source of assurance and a driver of “Pag-asa”</p>	<p>P4: Participants mentioned that their belief in God strengthens their resolve to remain responsible as parents and continue supporting their children from prison.</p> <p>P6: The participant always prays for the Lord to guide his family.</p>	<p>Participants shows how Filipino cultural values shape “Pag-asa” as an interplay between communal and purposeful actions</p>

DISCUSSION

1. What is “Pag-asa” for Tatay’s who serve long-term imprisonment?

The central theme "*Pag-asa: The family as a main source of “Pag-asa”*" shows that family is a key source of “Pag-asa” for Filipino fathers in prison. In the case of P1, his “Pag-asa” is focused on returning home to guide and care for his grandchildren. For P4, his children are the main reason he holds on to “Pag-asa”. Both participants express that the love and responsibility they feel for their family motivates them to endure their challenges. Their desire to provide for and be with their family after being released keeps their spirits strong. This theme is supported by their words, which highlight how family is a powerful source of “Pag-asa” for them.

Sub-Theme 1.1 "Family as Strength"

Participants P1 and P4 states that:

"Ang pag-asa po sa akin eh, makauwi. Yun lang naman para magabayan po mga apo po." - P1

"Ang mga anak ko." - P4

It highlights how the participants draw strength and "*Pag-asa*" from their family, which motivates them to keep going. P1 shares that his "*Pag-asa*" is to return home and guide his grandchildren, showing that his family, especially his grandchildren, gives him the strength to endure. P4 also emphasizes the importance of his children, stating that they are his source of strength. Both participants show that their family plays a key role in giving them the emotional support they need to stay hopeful. This sub-theme is evident in their words, as their love and responsibility toward their family help them remain strong in difficult circumstances. The theme is justified by their deep connection to family, which serves as a powerful motivator for their resilience.

The importance of family contact during incarceration is also highlighted by research that maintains that having strong family relationships enhances mental health and resilience. According to studies, those incarcerated individuals who are able to maintain family contact through visitation or other means have better coping mechanisms and psychological outcomes. This is similar to the experiences of participants P1 and P4, who find family to be a source of strength. Such support plays a key role in fostering resilience during difficult times (Prison Policy Initiative, 2021).

Sub-Theme 1.2 "Emotional Resilience for Family"

Participants P1 and P2 states that:

"Kasi mga anak po, okay naman po sila." "Yun, Kasi kaya ako lumalakas dahil sa kanila eh. Hihina ako, hindi ko na sila mayayakap paglabas po."

- P1

"Kahit na malungkot, okay lang maging masaya po. Para sa kanila." - P2

The motivations, which direct and fuel participants' emotional strength, include an urge to support the family and to be there with it. P1 indicates that his children keep him

going, and the thought of not being able to carry them along after being released will further weaken him, indicating how deeply his family motivates his resilience. Strength to draw from his love for children, the "Pag-asa" of getting reunited with his children. P2 expresses himself, saying he is already in pain but does not wish to be so because it might affect his family's feelings. Both participants confirm through this sub-theme that they believe that their emotional resilience is conditioned by their life situations with their families and their expectations for the future. The need to stay strong for their families gives them strength to endure the toughest situations, for emotional resilience in the service of one's loved ones is a very powerful drive in their lives.

P1 and P2 engage in conversations wherein they describe "Pag-asa" as heavily anchored on their families. For P1, "Pag-asa" translates to rekindling his relationship with his children, while for P2, it is moving forward positively for the family's sake. This indicates how "Pag-asa" derives so much from family relationships because the emotional point of strength during incarceration is basically that of being closely related. Research indicates that maintaining family ties leads to "Pag-asa" and enhanced mental health, thereby also improving the prospects for coping with difficulty and reintegrating following release (McKay et al., 2019; CSG Justice Center, 2024). Thus, "Pag-asa" is both a personal drive and a shared strength rooted in family connections.

Central Theme 2 "Pag-asa: "Pag-asa" through Faith"

Participants P3, P5 and P6 states that:

"Sa Panginoon, aasa sa Panginoon." - P3

"Sa Panginoon na rin po ma'am e." - P5

"Pray is number one yan. Kasi, makapangyarihan yan. Sa tulong ng "Panginoon, mayroon mga taong nagtitiwala...kung nandyan ang Diyos sa'yo, hindi ka papabayaan kahit kailanman." - P6

It highlights the role of faith in giving "Pag-asa" to Filipino fathers in prison. Participants P3, P5, and P6 all express their strong belief in God's power to help them through difficult times. P3 and P5 rely on their faith in God, while P6 believes that through prayer and God's help, people will trust and support them. Their words show that faith in God provides them with "Pag-asa" and the strength to face their struggles.

A factor by which faith gives "Pag-asa" and gives life to Filipino fathers in prisons, as your participants clearly and definitely demonstrated. Their words-some expressions during their time of struggles-as for example P3, with, "Sa Panginoon, aasa sa Panginoon," and P5 says that "Sa Panginoon na rin po ma'am e. Research supports this belief, showing how faith in God not only allows for resilience but also how it is a powerful source of emotional support. For example, prison chaplains in the Philippines offer inmates spiritual guidance and emotional aid during their hardships (Chaplains serving Philippine prison, 2020). Crossroads Prison Ministries is an example of such programs of mentoring where faith is transforming, where prisoners get a sense of purpose and emotional healing while also showing the capability to live very differently compared to an otherwise harsh environment within them. The following statement regarding power of prayer from P6 reveals the transformative process whereby "it ensures God's support as well as protection."

The central theme "Pag-asa: External Support System: Pillar of *"Pag-asa"* in Long-term Imprisonment" highlights how external support from loved ones strengthens *"Pag-asa"* for those in long-term imprisonment. P1 expresses that talking to his family, especially his grandchildren, through calls brings him joy and boosts his spirit, showing how emotional connection provides *"Pag-asa"*. Similarly, P6 shares that his *"Pag-asa"* is reinforced by the encouraging words of his children and wife, as they tell him to keep fighting and pray to God. Their support acts as a source of strength, making P6 feel more hopeful. Both participants show that encouragement and love from family members are key factors in maintaining *"Pag-asa"* while imprisoned. This theme is confirmed by their experiences, demonstrating how external support, especially from family, can serve as a crucial pillar of *"Pag-asa"* during long-term imprisonment.

Research indicates that ties to family have a significantly positive emotional impact on long-term prisoners. The primary part of that is regular communication with the family, mainly via telephone calls or letters. Family support helps in the maintenance of emotional resilience and makes it into an important pillar in time of long imprisonment (Crewe, 2020). This also agrees with studies that suggest life-sentenced prisoners cite family and faith to be their source of hope most at times (Kotova, 2018).

Sub-Theme 3.1 "Family Support"

Participant P1 and P6 states that:

"Pagka mayroon kami dito ng call center, makausap ko lang sila, masaya na ako. Makausap ko yung apo ko, halos galak na galak na ako." –P1

"Dahil sa mga anak ko, sabi pa, laban ka lang. Dahil sa mga sinasabi ng mga anak ko, asawa ko, laban ka lang. Pray sa Panginoon. Yung pag-asa na yun, lumalakas." –P6

This illustrates how the support from family members is vital in keeping the participants strong and maintaining their *"Pag-asa"*. P1 shares that even the simple act of talking to his family through a call center brings him happiness, especially when he communicates with his grandchildren. This interaction with his family gives him a sense of joy and motivates him to keep going. Similarly, P6 emphasizes how the encouragement from his children and spouse strengthens his resolve to keep fighting, as they tell him to stay strong and trust in God. The words of support from his family help P6 maintain *"Pag-asa"* and resilience in his difficult situation. Both participants demonstrate that family support, whether emotional or through words of encouragement, plays a significant role in sustaining *"Pag-asa"* during their time in prison.

The study from the University of the Philippines Institute of Population (UPPI) reveals that 1 in 3 Filipino youth grew up without both parents, a significant factor that affects their emotional and psychological development. This finding highlights the crucial role of family support in youth well-being. Growing up without the presence of both parents, particularly in the formative years, can lead to emotional instability, low self-esteem, and academic challenges, as children miss out on critical parental guidance and emotional support.

In the context of family support, the study underscores the importance of stable

family structures. The absence of parents, especially when children are left with limited or no emotional support, can hinder their ability to develop resilience and "Pag-asa". Family support is not only critical for providing emotional security but also for fostering academic and social success.

These findings align with broader research indicating that children in supportive, intact family environments are more likely to thrive, as strong family ties are associated with higher levels of well-being, emotional resilience, and coping ability during difficult times. University of the Philippines Population Institute, (2022).

Sub-Theme 3.2: "Act of Kindness from the Religious Support Groups and Community"

Participants P3 and P5 states that:

"Katulad ng RBO may nagbibigay regalo sa amin. Natutuwa ako sa ganon dahil naramdaman ko na may nagmamahal pa rin pala sa akin." –P3

"Sana sa mga biyaya ang galing sa religious group. Kulad mga sabon, toothpaste, dala ng religious." –P5

This highlights how acts of kindness from religious groups and the community help participants feel valued and supported. P3 mentions receiving gifts from the Religious Beneficiary Organization (RBO), which made him feel loved and appreciated, showing that such gestures can uplift someone in a difficult situation like imprisonment. Similarly, P5 appreciates the gifts, such as soap and toothpaste, brought by the religious group, recognizing them as valuable contributions that provide both physical and emotional comfort. These acts of kindness from religious and community groups not only address basic needs but also help maintain "Pag-asa" and a sense of connection with the outside world. The support they receive through such gestures contributes to the participants' emotional well-being, reinforcing the importance of community and faith in their lives. Both P3 and P5 demonstrate how the kindness of others plays a key role in sustaining "Pag-asa" while incarcerated.

One article that highlights the significant role of community pantries in the Philippines, a grassroots initiative that emerged during the COVID-19 pandemic as a direct response to the widespread need for food and necessities. This initiative, which was supported by various religious groups and community leaders, emphasizes acts of kindness and solidarity. The Church, through organizations like Caritas, encouraged the creation of community pantries to provide mutual aid, demonstrating how religious support groups can mobilize communities to offer tangible assistance, particularly during times of crisis.

This initiative aligns with the broader concept of acts of kindness from religious support groups, where faith-based organizations facilitate and promote community-driven charity efforts. These acts of kindness not only provide material assistance but also inspire hope, empathy, and a sense of shared responsibility within communities. The Catholic Bishops' Conference of the Philippines (CBCP) encouraged these community-driven initiatives as a way to embody Christian values of love and mutual care, offering a

model of how religious support can foster unity and collective well-being. Vatican News, (2021).

2. In what way does “*Pag-asa*” affect their everyday lives?

The central theme of "*Pag-asa: A Catalyst for Emotional Endurance and Strength of Filipino Incarcerated Tatays*" focuses on "*Pag-asa*" as a driving force for Filipino fathers (tatays) in prison to endure hardships and stay strong. P1 and P4 express how their "*Pag-asa*" for a better future, especially for their children, motivates them to keep going. P1 believes that staying strong will help him support his family once he is released, while P4 works multiple jobs with the "*Pag-asa*" of providing a better life for his children. Both participants show how "*Pag-asa*" fuels their emotional strength and determination to overcome their current struggles.

The "*Pag-asa*" and emotional strength that will help custodial parents are phone calls, letters, and visits, keeping them connected with family. This has been instrumental in helping them cope with the difficulties of imprisonment while looking forward to a future at least different from one devoid of their family. Further, the link performs a significant function of alleviating some of the emotional effects of incarceration on children, developing emotional endurance, and strengthening family ties (Kajstura, 2021).

Sub-Theme 1.1: "*Pag-asa* as Source of Strength for the Future"

Participant P1 and P4 states that:

"Ang pag-asa po sa akin eh, makauwi. Yun lang naman para magabayan po mga apo po." –P1

"Ang mga anak ko." –P4

This focuses on how "*Pag-asa*" gives the participants the strength to work toward a better future. P1 shares that his "*Pag-asa*" to work hard for his family after being released gives him the strength to endure. His desire to be strong and provide for his family motivates him to keep going. P4 expresses that his "*Pag-asa*" for freedom and a better life, especially for his children, drives him to work harder, even taking on two jobs to support them. Both participants highlight that their "*Pag-asa*" for a better future helps them stay strong and focused on their goals. This sub-theme is supported by their belief that "*Pag-asa*" for the future provides them with the strength to continue despite their current challenges. Their "*Pag-asa*" is a powerful motivator that keeps them looking forward to a brighter tomorrow.

The Fathers Building Futures Program is meant to equip incarcerated fathers with vital tools that enable them to stabilize their emotions, parent well, and be financially literate so they can avoid the intergeneration cycle of incarceration. This action emphasizes "*Pag-asa*" and preparation to restore families as part of elimination of emotional fueling and creating a hopeful vision for the future. In keeping open lines of communication while preparing fathers to manage their relationships and responsibilities, the initiative assists them to refocus on reintegration and building stronger connections with their children (Fathers Building Futures, 2021).

Sub-Theme 1.2: "Pag-asa as Strength to Endure"

Participant P1 and P2 states that:

"Kasi mga anak po, okay naman po sila." –P1

"Yun, Kasi kaya ako lumalakas dahil sa kanila eh. Hihina ako, hindi ko na sila mayayakap paglabas po." –P1

"Kahit na malungkot, okay lang maging masaya po. Para sa kanila." –P2

It has been pointed out that "Pag-asa" serves as strength among the participants in managing their challenges. As P6 stated, though prison has its difficulties and harshness, he believes that "Pag-asa" helps him endure and overcome moments of suffering: whether dealing with difficult persons or putting up with the harshness of the environment, his "Pag-asa" contributes in facing prison life challenges with resilience. P1 mentions that "Pag-asa" is his strength for his family, for he feels he needs to stay strong for them, especially when sick or going through difficult times, and says that even when he has moments of weakness, "Pag-asa" makes it possible for him to rise once more. Supported by their belief that "Pag-asa" serves to endure pain, challenges and isolation, and gives them emotional strength to continue to live; this sub-theme is meaningful. Hence the participants manifest that "Pag-asa" is a heaver in terms of life itself.

The theme of "Pag-asa" is, in these activities, being a much concern to research nowadays as it relates to an inspiration for emotional endurance and resilience in hardship within prison life, especially for an imprisoned father. This "Pag-asa" is what motivates most incarcerated parents to provide good lives for their children even with disconnection in prison. Studies underline the necessity of keeping family ties while behind prison walls. Studies show that this "Pag-asa" to reunite with family members, especially children, makes incarcerated fathers stronger and able to withstand prison life (Prison Policy Initiative, 2020; National Institute of Justice, 2020).

Keeping those bright links open regarding children-family approaches, such as visits and communications, is necessary. Such tying creates a large amount of such an environment in which wear, and emotional state-to-state transition processes continue being reduced along with symptoms of depression and aggressive behavior and is considered one of the major reasons one could sustain hope (Prison Policy Initiative, 2020). It is just at such times of the bond that emotional strength is provided, thus giving the motivation for said prison-bound father to continue against the odds of his present setting (National Institute of Justice, 2020).

The central theme, "Pag-asa: Strengthening and Challenging 'Pag-asa'," revolves around the idea that "Pag-asa" is to be fortified and challenged basically through faith. P1 still claims that his very strong faith has given him all the strength he needs to endure, stating how faith helps reinforce his "Pag-asa" in difficult times. P4 makes it clear that she considers it dependence on God, who because of her faith could go on. In fact, P6 also shows that "Pag-asa" is strengthened by a deeper trust in God because faith for him is a foundation for creating emotional buffer. All these indicate that their "Pag-asa" is not just a waiting time for a change; rather, it is waiting strengthened by faith that aids in becoming

resilient. The theme is developed by their personal experiences where faith is a contradictor of the difficulties they face and makes them possess "Pag-asa".

Sub-Theme 2.1: "Faith and Religion as a Source of Continued "Pag-asa" Amid Adversities"

Participants P1, P4, and P6 states that:

"Kasi malakas yung panalampalataya ko. Kaya di magtatalo yun." –P1

"Mananalig ako sa Panginoon para mabigyan ako ng lakas at magpatuloy sa buhay." –P4

"Ang nagpapatatag yan, yung pag-asa na yan, ay sa pamamagitan ng pananalig sa Panginoon." –P6

It illustrates how faith in God would make these participants hopeful and steadfast in times of adversity. P1 shows that he believes that a strong faith would be solid and keep him grounded, for it makes him hopeful because he would not have lost "Pag-asa". Indeed, P4 puts his trust in God and believes that God will grant him the strength to go through life when conditions are hard. Equally, P6 perceives faith as the very source of strength that fortifies his "Pag-asa," thus signifying that faith in God serves as a sustaining mechanism against adversities. This sub-theme obtains collective support from their belief that with faith, one can continue to endure and retain one's "Pag-asa." Their belief in religion thus becomes a strong supporting mechanism while they face adversities with confidence that they are not alone in confronting them.

The article Filipinos Mark 500 Years of Christianity: Connecting Them All at the Global Level is one that speaks much how Christianity resonates within the country within that year of 500 years. Faith and religion have been the pivots and center points of identity among Filipinos wherein they have become the hallmark from which Pag-asa and strength draw sustenance although in the past, they have been interrupted at certain points. It describes Pastruality and church involvement with that historical Christian connection into the sense of community-in local and global terms-to definitely bolster common "Pag-asa" and resilience through hardship. Filipinos would generally refer to faith as a very important thing in their lives, especially during times of testing. Overall, it casts an image of a role played by religion as a source of much larger "Pag-asa" and assurance. Discussing much more of the Filipino popular-religion, it could include the zeal towards valuing the Catholic faith that is very important at the individual and collective approach towards facing poverty, natural calamities, and political instability, all being described as challenges. It also highlights how Filipinos, through their faith, become a unified people of this global community that provides a larger spiritual and emotional backing in times of crisis. This study marks the significant juncture of 500 years that brought into place the long journey traversed by faith and religion in their sources of hope, especially among a people whose culture has depended upon such for emotional strength and solidarity and resilience. Hence, it would not only mean solace against the troubles of life but also breeds a sense of purpose, faith, and continuity-all leading to hope in the pages of future generations. (Zimmermann, 2021).

Sub-Theme 2.2: "Pessimism and Loss of Faith"

Participants P5, P6, and P4 states that:

“Parang wala na nga akong pag-asa doon kasi nga ano na eh dahil sa mga nakikita ko e.” –P5

“Wala akong pananalig sa Diyos, siguro yung pag-asa na yun mabubuwal sa akin.” –P6

“Nakakalungkot lang sana lang ay maalala nila yung paghihirap ko para sa pamilya ko noon tapos sa bandang huli dito lang pala makukulong.”—P4

It reveals how some participants lose "Pag-asa" and faith because of their situations. P5 says he feels like he has lost "Pag-asa" because he sees many bad things. Otherwise, P6 declares that without faith in God, it's only a matter of time before his "Pag-asa" fades away, in other words showing how the absence of faith brings on feelings of helplessness and no hope. This is also true for old P4, who feels pain and bitterness because he has sacrificed so much for his family, but has just ended up in prison. Evidence for this subtheme is present in the expressions of frustration and disappointment that the participants experience with their situations. These lead them away from feeling connected with "Pag-asa." Their experiences show that once faith in it is shaken or lost, the power to go on hoping in it becomes weak and leads the person to experience more difficulty in facing their struggles.

The role of religion in relation to mental health and well-being addresses how religion can potentially act as a buffer against adverse psychological effects. The attribute of possessing strong religious beliefs and practices holds true for those who cope better with stress, depression, and life challenges. On the other hand, it states that losing faith may lead to a less positive attitude toward life, purpose in living, and a potential detrimental effect on mental health.

The loss or decline of religious belief is emphasized in the article, which clearly shows how this would finally become positive for a life with more despair or hopelessness, probably in terms of pessimism itself. For example, when someone experiences a crisis of faith, that person is often unable to find meaning in that person's life. This leads to a negative attitude toward life. People who are faith challenged may not be able to cope very well with adversity; their lives are described as often leading to spiritual emptiness with poor emotional resilience because faith provides the scaffolding for "Pag-asa", hope, and sustenance in many things.

Such general psychological theories support the conducive effect of faith loss on the psychological root of instability, purposelessness, and disconnection—all the basic components that work to buffer pessimism. Push aside imperfectionism, and faith under all circumstances enriches well-being, engenders optimism, and connects to hope. Leontopoulou, S., & Zambelis, S. (2020).

Sub-Theme 2.3 “Pag-asa” Through Family and Communication

“Masaya po. Masayang-masaya. Tapos si Ma’am Cha, tuwan-tuwan rin “Kinumusta ko na lang sila eh. Sinabi ko na sabihin Lahat-lahat ng mga kapatid nya, sabihin nyo na lang na buhay pa rin ako.” –P5

“Isa lang yung nakakausap po, ma’am. Yung andon lang sa provincial jail, nakakausap po.” –P2

It highlights how communication with family members plays a crucial role in maintaining *“Pag-asa”* for the participants. P5 expresses joy and happiness from staying in touch with family, especially feeling uplifted when communicating with loved ones like Ma'am Cha. This connection helps him feel supported and keeps his *“Pag-asa”* alive, as he values staying in touch with his family. P2, on the other hand, mentions that he can only speak with one family member in the provincial jail, indicating that limited communication also keeps him hopeful, even if it's just with a few. Both participants rely on communication with their family to feel emotionally connected and supported, which helps them endure their time in prison. The presence of family contact, even if limited, is essential in maintaining their *“Pag-asa”*, showing that family relationships and communication are a critical source of strength.

Relating this to hope through family and communication, the article categorizes families into groups based on their communication styles: those that foster open communication and support, those that avoid confrontation, those that become defensive, and those that are dismissive. The first category, where open and empathetic communication is encouraged, is most aligned with the concept of *“Pag-asa”* through family. In these families, individuals are more likely to feel understood, supported, and hopeful, as effective communication nurtures trust and emotional bonding, key factors that promote a sense of security and hope. When families fail to communicate effectively or avoid difficult discussions, the result can be a sense of isolation, misunderstanding, and diminished hope. Families that engage in negative communication patterns, like defensiveness or dismissal, can contribute to feelings of helplessness and pessimism, making it harder for individuals to remain hopeful.

By emphasizing the role of healthy communication in strengthening family bonds and promoting well-being, the article supports the idea that family communication is essential for fostering hope and resilience in the face of adversity. Cohen, S. (2020).

3. How does *“Pag-asa”* affect their belief system as a *tatay*?

The participants would readily mention their family as a source of *“Pag-asa”* that, in turn, influences a nuanced positive belief system in their context. They noticeably mention their family with fondness and longing, often interspersed with bursts of unavoidable emotions. Despite being incarcerated for a long time, this familiar fondness for their family members implies a healthy, if not constant, communication between them and their family. These regulated visits and/or communication between and beyond the incarcerated life becomes a lifeline for them, becoming a wellspring of *“Pag-asa”* that they use to keep the lonely, mundane reality they face with beliefs that belie their context with a positive nature.

Sub-theme 1.1: Familial bonds inspire *“Pag-asa”*, which drives them to respond to their situation positively.

Participants P1, P2, P5 and P6 expressed that:

"Ang pag-asa po ay buhay pa ako, malakas at saka yung mga apo po, mga anak po. Yun, sila ang lakas po." -P1

"Para makita ko rin yung mga pamilya ko." -P2

"May pag-asa ako kasi yung pamilya ko." -P5

"Yung mga anak ko, sila ang lakas ko."-P6

It talks about how the families give strength to the participants and help them be hopeful and resilient. P1 expresses that his "Pag-asa" comes from being alive and strong and from his children's and grandchildren's love and support. Research studies have concluded that the love and support coming from family ties are a very important ingredient in strengthening emotional stability and hope during trying times (Fauziah et al., 2024). Similarly, P2 mentions that seeing his family again gives him "Pag-asa" and is a great motivator for him to go through. Which is echoed in the study where respondents indicated that family reunification during incarceration was a source of resilience. P5 states that his family is the biggest source of "Pag-asa", which means that he keeps a positive outlook due to their support. The study found further that strength in family support was essential in the sustainability of optimism and stability when being held behind bars. P6, for his part also believes his children were instrumental to him as well while admitting his family is the well of his strength within his confines. These reactions evidence the strength of love and attachment towards family as an inspiration for "Pag-asa" and the improvement that brings with it to cope with jail imprisonment.

Sub-Theme 1.2: "Pag-asa: Desire for Freedom and Reconnection"

Participants P2 and P3 states that:

"Kung maari po sana eh makauwi na sana... para makita ko rin yung mga pamilya ko." -P2

"Magbigyan ng pagkakataon, yun ang hinihintay ko. "Hinihintay ko lang ang pagkakataon na makalabas at makabalik sa pamilya ko." P5: "Yung pag-asa, ibig sabihin, may inaantay na kalayaan." -P3

This shows how the participants are hopeful to be free and to reunite with their families. P2 expresses his desire to be released so that he can once again be with his family, thereby showing how the desire to reconnect with loved one fuels *Pag-asa*. P3 says that he is waiting for the opportunity to go back to his family, and he says that *Pag-asa* is tied to the chance of being free again. P5 also links his *Pag-asa* to the anticipation of freedom, showing that *Pag-asa* for release is a major drive in his life. These statements reflect how the desire for freedom and reunion with family are powerful motivators, keeping the participants focused on a positive future. This sub-theme is supported by their strong yearning for the day they can leave prison and return to their loved ones, as noted by Song et al. (2024), who highlight the significant role of family ties in maintaining "Pag-asa" and resilience during incarceration.

Sub-Theme 1.3: "Pag-asa" as a Source of Resilience Despite Challenges"

Participants P2 and P4 states that:

"24 years na akong nakakulong. Nanalangin na lang ako sa Panginoon. Sana

palayain niya rin ako.” –P2

“Habang nabubuhay ay may Pag-asa.” –P4

This centers on how "Pag-asa" helps the participants remain strong in prison, no matter the hardships they have to go through. P2 says that after 24 years of imprisonment, he still prays to God, asking for freedom, and therefore "Pag-asa" keeps him resilient even after such a long time. P4 underscores that if he is living, then there is "Pag-asa", which means that "Pag-asa" in itself is a reason to continue, no matter what. Both participants show that "Pag-asa" gives them the strength to endure their difficult circumstances. This sub-theme is supported by the fact that they believe that "Pag-asa" is essential for survival and staying strong. Their words demonstrate that, even after decades of imprisonment, "Pag-asa" is always a source of strength.

The perspectives of "Pag-asa" by participants are reflected in the study by Ozturk et al. (2024), where Hope is an actual psychological foundation that assists them in relation to prison stay in dealing and enduring adversities. P2's basis on spiritual "Pag-asa" coincides with discoveries that "Pag-asa" inculcates the spirit of resilience even in the most severe circumstances. Similarly, P4 identifies life sources with "Pag-asa" in them. This is similar to the study revelations about hope delivering emotional stability and, therefore, a positive outlook when there are systemic challenges.

Central theme 2: “Pag-asa” as a foundation of positivity

The Participants found strength and optimism through their faith in God. According to P1, "Basta ako, kung sa Panginoon lang, may pag-asa pa. Expressing confidence that "Pag-asa" is possible if it is rooted in God. Similarly, P5 said, "Ang pag-asa ko sa Diyos, kahit anong mangyari," shows faith in God even in challenging times. P6 supported the same idea, "May pag-asa ako kasi yung pag-asa na mula sa Panginoon, talagang inaasahan ko yan. May assurance ako doon sa pag-asa ko na yan," highlighting a sense of security and positivity that "Pag-asa" comes from his faith in God. These excerpts justify the theme because all three participants used their faith as a source of "Pag-asa", helping them stay positive despite life's uncertainties.

Sub-Theme 2.1 “Pag-asa” as a Spiritual Anchor

Participant P1, P5, and P6 states that:

Basta ako, kung sa Panginoon lang, may pag-asa pa.” –P1

“Ang pag-asa ko sa Diyos, kahit anong mangyari.” –P5

“May pag-asa ako kasi yung pag-asa na mula sa Panginoon, talagang inaasahan ko yan. May assurance ako doon sa pag-asa ko na yan.” –P6

They rely on their faith in God as a strong source of "Pag-asa". P1 explains that his "Pag-asa" comes from God, believing that if he has faith, there is "Pag-asa" for him. P5 shares that his "Pag-asa" is entirely in God, no matter what happens, indicating that his faith keeps him grounded. P6 emphasizes that his "Pag-asa" comes from God and that he fully trusts in this "Pag-asa", feeling assured that his faith will guide him. These statements show that for the participants, their spiritual beliefs provide a strong foundation

of "Pag-asa". This sub-theme relies on the faith that they had in a God who served as their spiritual anchor during challenging times, and such must have been the elixir within the theme. And so it was that through faith in God that they went on to meet their challenges and thus strengthened the element of spirituality in sustaining "Pag-asa".

Sub-Theme 2.2: "Pag-asa as Endurance"

Participant P6 and P5 states that:

"Kahit anong mangyayari sa buhay ko, may pag-asa ako. Kahit nandito lang ako mamamatay, may assured na ako sa buhay ko." –P6

"May pag-asa ako na kahit anong mangyari sa buhay ko, malalampasan ko ito." – P5

It indicates how "Pag-asa" actually assists the participants in grasping the different kinds of events occurring in their lives, whether intruding through death or hardship. P6 is one who states that whatever happens, he just holds on to "Pag-asa" even if he dies in prison, an illustration that "Pag-asa" impresses on him a kind of assurance and strength to face the unknown. "I have this hope that whatever adversity he goes through, he can always surpass those: "Because it shows how hope endures and sustains him." It's just a matter of learning that "Pag-asa", according to this participant wherein it states that it's all about struggling through to a hopeful future. It, by the way, can be summarized to show the sub-theme that all believe "Pag-asa" helps him remain resilient, despite circumstances. As evidenced by their words, these connections above show that for a source called "Pag-asa", endurance can be pushed through regarding the time when these students experience harsh times.

A study by Ocampo (2022) examines the role that spirituality plays in resilience: praying and communal worship create hope and emotional stability. Such approaches create purpose that provides anchorage during difficult times. The research reflects the perceptions of the participants themselves, articulated in the general theme "Hope as a Foundation of Positivity." P1, P5, and P6 appreciate the significance of faith in God as one source of strength and "Pag-asa," which corresponds to what Ocampo tells about spirituality as a source of stability while experiencing misery. Their belief that "as long as they have faith, there is "Pag-asa". reflects the role of spirituality in promoting resilience and optimism. Also, reliance of participants on God for endurance, especially in times of adversity, fits into the conclusion of the study, that faith-based "Pag-asa" is an active psychological strategy, which enables the human being to cope with the existential crises with resilience. This makes spirituality more important in holding onto "Pag-asa" while standing on the uncertainty of life with determination.

The central theme "Pag-asa: Faith, Community, and Resilience as Cultural Roots of "Pag-asa" in Filipino Imprisonment" shows how faith, community, and resilience help Filipino fathers in prison stay hopeful. Participants P2, P3, P4, and P5 all mention how they find strength through their faith and involvement in community activities, especially those related to the church. P2 talks about attending church to find peace, while P3 and P4 highlight the importance of gatherings and religious activities as a source of support. P5 shares how learning and attending church gatherings after cooking give him a sense of "Pag-asa" and strength. These practices of faith and community engagement reflect

the cultural values that help them cope with their situation. The theme is supported by their experiences, showing that faith and community play a central role in maintaining "Pag-asa" during imprisonment.

Filipino resilience attached very much to cultural variables such as family and faith while active in the community profoundly undercut general external support for many types of suffering and hardship and produce quite a strong source of adaptive individual personal strength to confront an adverse time. For example, attending church and community participation creates an emotional rather than welfare-based progressive system for individuals dealing with adversities, particularly often involving Filipino fathers who have been imprisoned (Baldonado & Castillo, 2020).

Moreover, the traditional value of bayanihan, or mutual assistance, has been marked as one pillar of Filipino fortitude. It creates the sense that even family and community can steer the way to the path of safety or hope to save oneself or unit from being lost in perplexities. This will create an irrevocable link of bondedness for the incarcerated individual (Reyes & Santos, 2023).

Sub-Theme 3.1: "Religious Practices of Filipino Incarcerated Fathers as Reinforcement of "Pag-asa"

Participants P2, P3, P4, and P5 states that:

"Mayos naman po, ma'am. Ang pag-ano nila ang mga ransok-ransok namin. Kumupunta na lang ako doon sa Simbaan ng Katoliko." –P2

"Nanampalataya tuwing sabado ay may salo-salo. Every other Saturday iyon at ngayong sabado may salo-salo ulit kami." –P3

"Sumasama na lang kami sa mga gawain sa simbahan." –P4

"Pag tapos ako magluto, umaattend ako para karagdang kaalaman. Masasabi niyo po bang parang nagdadagdag po yan sa pag-asa? Opo, opo. Malaking dagdag talaga." –P5

It shows how religious practices help the participants strengthen their "Pag-asa" while incarcerated. P2 mentions that he attends Catholic church services, finding peace and connection through religious activities, which provide comfort and "Pag-asa". P3 shares that he participates in faith-based gatherings every other Saturday, showing that regular spiritual practices help him maintain "Pag-asa" and belief. P4 also emphasizes joining church activities as a way to stay spiritually connected, which reinforces his sense of "Pag-asa". P5 explains that after cooking, he attends church to gain knowledge, and he feels that these practices greatly increase his "Pag-asa". This sub-theme is supported by the participants' consistent engagement in religious practices, highlighting how these activities help them find strength, "Pag-asa" and a sense of community during their time in prison. Their participation in religious activities reinforces their "Pag-asa" and resilience in difficult circumstances.

It has now been well examined about how religious practices instill "Pag-asa" and emotional resilience in inmates. It is because attending church, prayer meetings, or faith-

based gathering leaves precious little time for these incarcerated fathers from the Philippines to engage in any behavior that may cause them stress. Most studies show that such religious practices help in developing capacity among inmates to deal with stress and fuel a hope for an improved future (Galanter, 2020). Attending religious rituals owes much toward coping-complex mechanisms, providing ones with purpose and community during isolation (Koenig et al., 2021).

Faith comes in handy as a *tambal* for Filipino family ties and at times more as a compass in the life direction. Research has indicated that attending religious services among Filipino inmates does not only bring psychological comfort but also strengthens their hope for re-integration and provision of support for their families once free (Trinidad, 2020). This can be further highlighted by the extracts from interviews where participants stated that being religious makes them feel more hopeful and emotionally strong, thus showing the power of faith in adversity (Galanter, 2020; Koenig et al., 2021).

Sub-Theme 3.2: "Pag-asa through Community and Purposeful Actions and Self-Reliance"

Participants P6 and P1 states that:

"Yung ginagawa namin dito, kung talagang mayroong kang sight sa pag, makamit mong pag-asa, gumawa kang mabuti. Ang ginagawa ko dito, puro kabutihan para makamit ko yung inaasam ko na pag-asa." –P6

"Ang ginagawa ko, nagteterapi ako. Nabubuhay ko rin yung sarili ko. Kaya minsan, wala akong tineterapi sa akin. Lord, bigyan mo ko may terapi po para may pera. Meron naman. Binibigyan na po ako." –P1

Participants' actions and self-reliance, in fact, become their "Pag-asa". P6 believes that "Pag-asa" comes through good action and motivation. By doing good deeds in prison, he works toward his "Pag-asa". According to P1, he still has hope, but through purposeful actions like therapy, while relying on himself. He said he prays for the resources he needs because he feels that his "Pag-asa" was awarded when help comes. This subtheme is further corroborated by the idea that if you try to contribute positively to the environment and then rely on your own abilities toward changing circumstances, "Pag-asa" remains alive for both. Furthermore, both participants demonstrate that being self-reliant and deliberately acting strengthens one's "Pag-asa" for a better future.

The role of "Pag-asa", purposeful actions, and self-reliance in promoting emotional endurance among incarcerated individuals has been established through research studies. Programs like Hope for Prisoners, based on the premise that hope arises as much from the community as it does from personal empowerment and skills training, are following actions that are likely to bring meaningful effects: in terms of vocational training or contribution in the environment-enhancing actions-these kinds of actions fortify emotional tolerance and strengthen hope for future aspirations (Hope for Prisoners, 2024).

Research conducted by Brookings Institution also stresses that hope for a specific future is what most prisoners express. Many believe performing deliberate acts-one finds

a job or reunited with family-is enough to direct them toward change for the better. These findings reinforce the argument that self-reliance and involvement in purposeful activities give prisoners a source of hope despite preferring imprisonment (Brookings, 2020).

The central theme "Pag-asa: Spiritual Faith Sustaining "Pag-asa" in Long-Term Imprisonment" emphasizes how faith helps prisoners maintain "Pag-asa" over long periods of imprisonment. P6 describes how prayer, or talking to God, is essential for maintaining his "Pag-asa" and strength. P1 shares that his belief in God is the most important thing, as he feels God helps him through difficult times. P4 states that keeping focus on God is key to maintaining "Pag-asa", as God is the source of "Pag-asa". P5 highlights that without faith in God, his "Pag-asa" would collapse, showing that prayer and belief are his foundation. These statements demonstrate that spiritual faith is a powerful and sustaining force, keeping "Pag-asa" alive for the participants during their long-term imprisonment.

Sub-Theme 4.1 "Power of Prayer"

Participants P5, P6, and P1 states that:

"Masasabi ko sa kanila rin, huwag tayo mawalan ng pag-asa. Habang nabubuhay tayo, may pag-asa tayo." –P5

"Binabahagi ko sa kanila. Mananatili lang tayo sa panalangin." –P6

"Gusto kong matuloy yung mga project ko para mapahanga ko ang mga anak ko."
–P1

It reflects how prayer serves as a key source of "Pag-asa" and strength for the participants. P6 highlights that prayer is essential for staying connected with God, describing it as "number one" and an ongoing conversation with the Lord. P1 expresses trust in God's help, showing that prayer reassures him that God is always there for support. P4 emphasizes that focusing on God and staying centered in Him is crucial for maintaining "Pag-asa", further stressing that God is the ultimate source of "Pag-asa". P5 also shares that constant prayer is vital to his sense of "Pag-asa", suggesting that without faith in God, his "Pag-asa" would collapse. All these statements demonstrate that for these participants, prayer is not just an act of faith, but a powerful tool to remain hopeful and resilient during their time in prison.

There are studies which indeed illuminate that the prisoners often seek prayer and other spiritual practices as a source of emotional healing and resilience. With regard to this aspect, during the global pandemic of COVID-19, Prison Fellowship has recorded increased demand for Bibles and spiritual resources in prisons. These associations with regular prayer and Bible study have reportedly bestowed upon the inmates, a rekindled hope which is supported by the belief that faith is important to their emotional strength and eventual transformation (Prison Fellowship, 2020).

The Bible is a great demonstration of a prayer healing program for incarcerated people. For example, by studying the Bible and praying, both men and women in facilities in the United States witnessed emotional healing and spiritual rejuvenation. Such programs can demonstrate that prayer, in combination with the Bible and community

support, is a powerful force in rendering participants healed and hopeful in even the worst circumstances (American Bible Society, 2020).

Sub-Theme 4.2 "Encouraging and Guiding Others"

Participants P6, P1, P4, and P5 states that:

P6: Mananatili lang tayo sa panalangin. Kasi, prayer is number one yan. Prayer is talking to the Lord."

P1: "Ang pinaka number one kasi dito... may inaasahan ako na mayroong Diyos na tumutulong sa akin."

P4: "Basta lagi lang tayong nakasentro sa Panginoon dahil siya ang Pag-asa."

P5: "Lagi akong manalangin. Kung wala akong pananalig sa Diyos, siguro yung pag-asa na yun mabubuwal sa akin."

It shows how the participants use their experiences to inspire "Pag-asa" and guide others. P5 encourages people around him to keep "Pag-asa" alive, emphasizing that as long as we are alive, there is always "Pag-asa". P6 shares his belief in the power of prayer, offering it as advice to others to help them stay strong and hopeful. P1 expresses his desire to complete his projects, not only for personal growth but also to impress and inspire his children. These actions demonstrate that the participants not only rely on "Pag-asa" for themselves but also share their strength with others, helping them stay hopeful and focused. By guiding and encouraging others, they turn their personal "Pag-asa" into a collective source of strength.

Since prisons have also been well documented in the recent studies regarding the importance of motivation and guidance, especially for themselves, those studies have defined "Pag-asa" not only as something usually rooted in faith, but also as something that helps people deal with their situations and helps direct others to the very same situations through people like participant P1, P4, or P5, who all underscore dependence on prayer and faith and share with others for a joint internal resource of emotional support and strength.

Research confirms the understanding that "Pag-asa" and resilience can be strengthened by peer support and mentorship so that individual struggles will become opportunities for communal growth. The same principle applies to prison inmates actively involved in such supportive relationships-whether faith-based or through mentorship-as these individuals ultimately develop a sense of mission, resilience, and the desire to help others through their struggles (Prison Fellowship, 2023; SGT Lawyer, 2023). Further, encouraging oneself lends very well to emotional fortitude because it generates a cycle of mutual sustainability reinforcing hope and perseverance (APA, 2022).

Encouraging others to stay strong and hopeful replicates one of the most fundamental parts of resilience, that is, the individual's individual hope becoming a collective source of strength (Prison Fellowship, 2023; SGT Lawyer, 2023).

4. How does their belief in "Pag-asa" influence their role in fulfilling their duties to their children?

It shows how "Pag-asa", faith, and family drive Filipino fathers in prison to stay strong and hopeful. P1 shares that his family, especially his loved ones, are his main source of strength and influence, giving him "Pag-asa" to keep going. P4 expresses how his family "Pag-asa" for their reunion, which motivates him to stay hopeful and work towards it. P5 promises his family that they will reunite if he stays alive, showing his strong faith in a future together. This theme is supported by their words, as all three participants see their family as a reason to keep going and remain hopeful. Their sense of responsibility to their families fuels their faith and "Pag-asa" for a better future after prison.

Sub-Theme 1.1 "Family as a Support Mechanism and a Source of Pag-asa"

Participants P4 and P6 states that:

"Sinasabi ko sa kanila na h'wag magkalimot sa Panginoon."- P4

"Basta si Lord nandyan sa'yo, hindi ka pababayaan e. Nanalangin ako lagi na, Panginoon, huwag mong pabayaan pamilya ko." - P6

It shows how the family of the participants play an important role in giving them "Pag-asa" and strength. P1 shares that his family is his strength and inspiration, showing how their support keeps him going. P4 expresses that his family hopes to reunite and become whole again, which provides him with motivation and "Pag-asa" for the future. P5 conveys that he tells his family to keep hoping that they will reunite if he is released, which strengthens his resolve to stay hopeful. This sub-theme is supported by the participants' belief that their families' love and support are key factors in maintaining "Pag-asa" during their time in prison. Their words highlight that their families not only inspire "Pag-asa" but also help them cope with the challenges of incarceration. The family connection serves as a powerful support system, making them resilient in the face of adversity. The study Family Support and Well-Being from BMC Public Health (2024), emphasizes the critical role that family support plays in improving individuals' overall health and psychological resilience. This study aligns well with the concept of family as a support mechanism and a source of "Pag-asa", highlighting that strong family ties offer emotional stability, increase life satisfaction, and provide the necessary social network during times of adversity.

In particular, the study outlines how family support can significantly buffer the effects of stress, reduce mental health risks, and promote adaptive coping mechanisms in challenging situations. By offering emotional encouragement, practical assistance, and a sense of belonging, family structures are integral to fostering hope, especially in contexts where external resources or support systems might be limited.

This aligns with the broader understanding that families serve as the first line of defense against various stressors and can act as a central pillar of hope for individuals, helping them overcome difficulties and face life's challenges with optimism. (An et. al, 2024).

Sub-Theme 1.2 "Faith and Religion as a Source of Assurance and a Driver of "Pag-asa"

Participants 4 and 6 states that:

"Sinasabi ko sa kanila na h'wag magkalimot sa Panginoon."- P4

“Basta si Lord nandyan sa’yo, hindi ka pababayaan e. Nanalangin ako lagi na, Panginoon, huwag mong pabayaan pamilya ko.” - P6

It accentuates the efficacy of faith and practice in religion for the participants, creating a sense of security and "Pag-asa". P4 says he encourages one to remember God in an attempt to show that faith in God has served as his bearings and reassurance. P6, on the other hand, trusts that his existence is guaranteed by God's continuous presence in his life; as such, he is praying for his family's welfare, and he collects further his "Pag-asa". This subtheme finds manifestation in their reliance on God for reassurance and strength, which may make things seem more assurable through all the rigors of life. Both of these participants derive comfort and inspiration from their spiritual beliefs, the basis of "Pag-asa" being faith. This link through God directs them to rehabilitating issues relating to imprisonment and the combining acts of strength and hope for the future.

Although in frontiers in psychology-the role of faith in coping with adversity (2021)- has probed the influence of faith and religion in the development of psychological resilience, the role of faith in providing solace and spurring "pag-asa". It has been found to be the other case that people who manage to derive strength from their religious beliefs are usually better prepared to deal with strains and adversities. Faith provides a sense of meaning and purpose, which in turn cultivates "Pag-asa" and emotional stability in trying times.

This aligns with the broader notion that faith and religion serve as powerful tools for individuals to manage uncertainty, improve mental health, and navigate life's challenges with an enduring sense of "Pag-asa". The study further discusses how religious practices, such as prayer and attending services, can offer a supportive community and a constant source of comfort, reinforcing one's belief that they are not alone in their struggles. These practices help reduce feelings of isolation and despair, key components in cultivating hope (Almeida et al., 2021).

Conclusions

The research on Pag-asa among long-term prisoners reveals that among Tatays, their hope is basically anchored on the family, faith in God, and communal practices. This becomes an important source of strength to fathers when facing life imprisonment, through which they could sometimes endure suffering, although they also suffer emotional feelings of guilt at times and hopelessness resulting from unfulfilled responsibilities.

The research assumptions were nuanced validation. First of all, it confirmed the connection of *Pag-asa* and their paternal roles, owing to the family ties inspired resilience, and yet the fathers were exposed to inadequate feeling. Second, *Pag-asa* proved to maintain resilience, but her degree changed with particular events and available outside help. Thirdly, family's influence, religious practices, and community involvement were marking the shaping of *Pag-asa* and the sustaining of emotional endurance.

In summary, *Pag-asa* forms the heart of the resiliency, belief systems, and fatherhood experiences of long-term imprisoned *Tatays*. Family, faith, and community are mainly sources of *Pag-asa*, however, individual differences suggest the need for

contextually responsive interventions in strengthening these sources of hope. This study points to the promise of *Pag-asa* in empowering fathers to overcome imprisonment and remain active members of their families and communities.

Recommendations

To maintain *Pag-asa* among the incarcerated fathers, the researchers recommend strengthening family ties by initiating programs that promote both physical and virtual visitations for fathers to be able to hold on to their loved ones. Emotional support services through social workers and psychologists will also help both inmates and their families cope with the challenges of separation. Faith-based programs, such as chaplaincy and religious programming, should be extended to continue the spiritual rebuilding aspect of *Pag-asa*. The peer mentoring and leadership program with prison communities could also facilitate increased resilience in order to establish meaning.

Rehabilitation efforts should target the provision of vocational training and self-improvement programs for equipping the fathers with skills for readmission. Further, mental health counseling and psychosocial support should be available to assist inmates in the management of feelings such as guilt and hopelessness. Family reintegration programs, parenting workshops, and communication training programs should be available to prepare the fathers for their responsibilities after release. Finally, collaboration among government agencies, NGOs, and religious organizations must be encouraged in building a sustainable support system. These will help the inmates maintain *Pag-asa*, build family ties, and develop resiliency toward successful reintegration into society.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured all ethical considerations by providing the participants with a consent form to sign. This ensured that all the participants were cooperating willingly and were not coerced to take part in the study. Moreover, the form indicated that the researchers are committed to maintaining their responsibility of not revealing any information that would be provided by the participants.

Research, interviews, consultation services, or similar ventures without the participants' informed consent are punishable under the law. The law clearly stated that all individuals functioning as respondents or participants must first be oriented and asked to approve the provision of information and for such information to be used and processed. Similarly, they should be assured that all documents, information, and recordings they provide or are a part of would be kept safely. Conclusion In a nutshell, the researchers, interviewers, or any person asking for information from others had the responsibility to explain the necessity of participants' disclosure of information. They were also mandated to advise participants on the risks of privacy, especially during electronically conducted and recorded data-gathering procedures (PAP, 2022).

This also implied that the Data Protection Act was enacted to ensure people's privacy concerning their human rights. It would guarantee private information and communication systems from invasion by the private sector or government.

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